

IMPROVEMENT OF THE PROCESSES OF PREPARING FUTURE TEACHERS FOR PROFESSIONAL-PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS THROUGH DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract. This article highlights effective methods and tools for improving the processes of preparing future teachers for professional and pedagogical activities in higher education institutions using digital technologies, as well as their specific features.

Keywords: digital technology, lesson, internet, decree, decision, education system.

Abstract. V stat'ye rassmatrivayutsya effektivnyye metody i sredstva sovershenstvovaniya protsessov podgotovki budushchikh uchiteley k professional'no-pedagogicheskoy deyatelnosti v organizatsiyakh vyshego obrazovaniya s ispolzovaniyem tsifrovyykh tekhnologiy, a takzhe ikh osobennosti.

Key words : digital technology, education, internet, posting, posting, system education.

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Introduction . The progress of large-scale reforms being implemented in our republic is also having a positive impact on the education system. Today, digital technologies are developing rapidly and require keeping up with the times in every field. In this era, when the speed of information acquisition and use has increased significantly, the use of digital technologies in the education system is of great importance in improving the quality of education and educating socially active youth. Previously, we conducted educational programs in the traditional way, that is, lectures through large-sized books and manuals. This, in turn, did not ensure such a high quality of education. Currently, the process of digitization of education has begun to improve the quality of education. The current state of the education system is characterized by the increasing role of non-traditional educational technologies. With their help, the assimilation of knowledge by the learner is much faster than with traditional technologies. These technologies change the nature of the

development, acquisition and dissemination of knowledge, making it possible to deepen and expand the content of the studied subjects, quickly update it, use more effective teaching methods, and also significantly expand access to education for everyone. Research materials and methodology.

We answer the question of what digital technology is as follows: it is a modern form of business . In which the main factor of production and management is a large set of digital data and the process of their processing. The practical use of the results obtained allows us to achieve much greater efficiency compared to traditional forms of business. Examples include various automated production processes, 3D technology, cloud technologies, remote medical services, production and delivery of products using smart technologies, storage and sale of various goods.

When education is provided through digital technologies, the methods of learning become easier for learners. In this case, multimedia, overhead projectors, computers, laptops, televisions connected to the Internet, telephone lines, smart boards, and projectors play the role of the educational system. Conducting classes with such tools for educators ensures an increase in the quality of education. We all know that the use of digital technologies in online classes gives good results [4]. In the conditions of today's New Uzbekistan, it is natural for the main tasks of the education system to be enriched in content and its social functions to improve. One of such social tasks is the development of strategies that incorporate all components of the formation of students' competencies in the application and use of digital technologies in education, which should constitute the main goal of the system in today's information age. Based on this goal, a number of legislative acts and decrees and decisions of the head of our state have been adopted and put into practice in our country. The Head of our state Sh.M. Mirziyoyev has set the following main directions for the further development of education and science in the new period of development of Uzbekistan: "...to prepare a new generation of personnel with high intellectual and spiritual potential, capable of coming up with new initiatives and ideas for the development of the country and implementing them, to form the necessary skills and knowledge in graduates of educational institutions so that they become modern professionals, and to create a system of automation and comprehensive analysis of education management using modern information and communication technologies, to further develop electronic resources and distance learning, to popularize professions in the IT field among students and to introduce highly effective international practices into the education system, and to carry out systematic work on including republican educational institutions in prestigious international ratings" [1]. Research results. The opening of Wi-Fi zones and IT parks will greatly contribute to the development of the digital education system . It is

possible to develop the skills of educators to work with digital technologies and organize various open courses via the Internet. This, in turn, will help educators work more on themselves and further improve the quality of education due to competition. In addition, digital technologies, the introduction of artificial intelligence technology, will help to detect tax evasion, prevent fraud, analyze data and automate repetitive processes, and increase transparency, while big data - Big data - will allow tax authorities to store and process large amounts of information, better predict revenues, and improve document exchange between payers and tax authorities. The adoption of digital technologies is occurring faster than any other innovation in human history : in just two decades, digital technologies have managed to cover about 50 percent of the population of developing countries and transform societies with their help [2]. For example, in the healthcare sector, advanced technologies based on the use of artificial intelligence are helping to save human lives, detect diseases, and increase life expectancy. In the education sector, the provision of virtual learning environments and distance learning has allowed students to participate in programs that they would not otherwise have had the opportunity to participate in. In addition, the use of blockchain-based systems will make it easier to use public services , increase the responsibility of the institutions providing them, and the use of artificial intelligence will make processes less bureaucratic. Big data can also lead to more flexible and accurate policies and programs. In the new era of development of our country, the special attention paid by the head of our state to the automation of education management through the use of information and communication technologies, the further development of electronic resources and distance learning, and the popularization of IT professions among students shows how high the role and importance of digital technologies in the education system is. In today's era of globalization, it is difficult to imagine our daily life without information and communication technologies, computers and the Internet. That is why today digital technologies are gradually entering all spheres of our daily life and becoming an integral part of social life. It is precisely with this important aspect in mind that more than 10 higher educational institutions have been established in our country, which train specialists in the field of engineering and digital technologies, which is also an indication of the great importance of digital technologies not only in such areas as economics and politics, but also in the education system. We can point to the fact that the main reason for the popularization of the use of digital technologies in the education system is the presence of convenient aspects not only for teachers, but also for students. For example, students have the opportunity to receive education when and where they want . In addition, by using digital technologies in education, we can achieve the following: – online or distance education of students in regions with a shortage of teaching staff; – teachers

and students can obtain, search, distribute and use information on the subject they want from the Internet; – increasing the efficiency of education, reducing the cost of time and money based on the use of digital technologies in the system; – by applying digital technologies to the educational process, we will have the opportunity to monitor not only the students' mastery of subjects, but also the extent to which they are mastering knowledge and their readiness for problem situations, the formation of critical thinking in them, as well as the development of students' abilities to work independently. Today, the main factor in the active introduction of digital technologies into the educational process is their effectiveness in positively changing the quality of lessons. An important factor in further improving this level of quality is the development of new strategic projects for the use of various teaching aids and digital technologies, the improvement of regulatory and legal documents for their introduction into the field, and the establishment of centers that include classrooms, laboratories, and media studios equipped with highly efficient digital devices [3].

Conclusion. Based on the above considerations, we can conclude that the use of digital technologies in the education system, firstly, ensures the effectiveness of teaching, secondly, prepares various illustrations, videos, visual aids, handouts related to the teaching process, and thirdly, improves the skills of teachers and educators in using multimedia products, computer equipment, Internet tools and applying them in the teaching process. Based on the above conclusions, the following are required: firstly, to create a continuous methodological service system aimed at forming the skills of teachers in using digital technologies; secondly, to follow the necessary recommendations, such as rational and targeted use of digital technologies and the formation of the ability of participants in the educational process to adapt to lessons organized on the basis of digital technologies.

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